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Tahririyat manzili: 150107

Farg'ona shahri, Farg'ona ko'chasi, 86 -
uy

Тел. +998971003888

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E-mail: alferganus.ltd@gmail.com

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Address of the editorial office:

150107

Fergana city, Fergana str., 86.

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Адрес редакции: 150107

г. Фергана, ул. Ферганская, 86

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Muminova, Elnorakhon**Abdukarimovna**

*Doctor of Economics, Professor,
Department of Economics,
Fergana Polytechnic Institute*

**Uraimzhonov, Azizbek Rakhmonjon
ugli**

*Assistant,
Department of Economics
Fergana Polytechnic Institute*

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IMPROVEMENT OF TRANSFORMATION PROCESSES DEVELOPMENT MECHANISMS OF ELECTRO TECHNICAL INDUSTRIAL ENTERPRISES AND EXPANSION OF THEIR ECONOMIC POTENTIAL IN THE FIELD IN UZBEKISTAN

Abstract. *This article discusses the issues of improving the development of transformation processes at industrial enterprises. The purpose of this study is to assess the state of the electronic industry in Uzbekistan and to propose solutions for its development. According to the results of the study, today the electronic industry of Uzbekistan has the largest number of employees in the industrial group of the region. In addition, net product and business income are growing rapidly in this sector. In particular, in the research work, analyses were made on the creation of new production capacities in the electrical industry in 2021–2022 and the launch of investment projects that will be implemented within the framework of the production diversification program.*

Keywords: *industry, transformation, economy, mechanism, method, development, electronics, electrical equipment, Uzbekistan.*

ELEKTROTEXNIKA SANOATI KORXONALARINI RIVOJLANTIRISH MEXANIZMLARINI O'ZGARTIRISH JARAYONLARINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH VA ULARNING O'ZBEKISTONDAGI IQTISODIY SALOHIYATINI KENGAYTIRISH

Muminova, Elnoraxon Abdugarimovna
*iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, professor,
"Iqtisodiyot" kafedrasini,
Farg'ona politexnika instituti*

Uraimjonov, Azizbek Rahmonjon ugli
*Assistent,
"Iqtisodiyot" kafedrasini
Farg'ona politexnika instituti*

Annotasiya. Ushbu maqolada sanoat korxonalarining transformatsion jarayonlarini rivojlantirishni takomillashtirish masalalari muhokama qilinadi. Ushbu tadqiqotning maqsadi O'zbekistondagi elektron sanoatning holatini baholash va uni rivojlantirish bo'yicha yechimlarni taklif qilishdan iborat. O'rganish natijalariga ko'ra, bugungi kunda O'zbekiston elektron sanoati mintaqaning sanoat guruhida eng ko'p xodimlarga ega; Bundan tashqari, ushbu sohada sof mahsulot va biznes daromadlari tez sur'atlar bilan o'sib bormoqda. Jumladan, tadqiqot ishida 2021-2022 yillarda elektrotexnika sanoatida yangi ishlab chiqarish quvvatlarini yaratish va ishlab chiqarishni diversifikatsiya qilish dasturi doirasida amalga oshiriladigan investitsiya loyihalarini ishga tushirish bo'yicha tahlillar amalga oshirilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: sanoat, transformatsiya, iqtisodiyot, mexanizm, usul, rivojlanish, elektronika, elektr jihozlari, O'zbekiston.

СОВЕРШЕНСТВОВАНИЕ ПРОЦЕССОВ ТРАНСФОРМАЦИИ МЕХАНИЗМОВ РАЗВИТИЯ ЭЛЕКТРОТЕХНИЧЕСКИХ ПРОМЫШЛЕННЫХ ПРЕДПРИЯТИЙ И РАСШИРЕНИЕ ИХ ЭКОНОМИЧЕСКОГО ПОТЕНЦИАЛА В В УЗБЕКИСТАНЕ

Муминова, Элнорахон Абдукаримовна
*доктор экономических наук, профессор,
кафедра "Экономика",
Ферганский политехнический институт*
Ураимжонов, Azizbek Рахмонжон угли
*Ассистент,
Кафедра «Экономика»
Ферганский политехнический институт*

Аннотация. В данной статье рассматриваются вопросы трансформационных процессов на промышленных предприятиях. Цель данного исследования оценка состояния электронной промышленности в Узбекистане и предоставление предложений по её развитию. Согласно исследованиям, на сегодняшний день электронная промышленность Узбекистана имеет наибольшую численность занятых в промышленной группе региона. Более того, чистый продукт и доход от бизнеса в этом секторе быстро растут. В частности, в научно-исследовательской работе проведен анализ создания новых производственных мощностей в электротехнической отрасли в 2021-2022 годах и запуска инвестиционных проектов, которые будут реализованы в рамках программы диверсификации производства.

Ключевые слова: промышленность, трансформация, экономика, механизм, метод. разработка, электроника, электрооборудование, Узбекистан

Introduction

Over the past decades, the world has been rapidly moving towards a radically new type of economy, where digital technologies are becoming the main tool for its development and increasing competitiveness.

Digital transformation is a global and global trend that affects both developed and developing countries of the world, and digital technologies are increasing the trends of importance in accelerating the development of the economic systems of most countries.

Electronic industry enterprises have promoted efficiency in production and business and made great contributions to the development of the industry in particular and the economy of the province in general. In the coming period, the problem is that it is necessary to have appropriate directions and solutions to improve the efficiency of electronic industry enterprises, ensure sustainable development in the future, towards a common goal of socio-economic development in Uzbekistan.

Further deepening of the reforms carried out on the development of the electrical engineering industry, attracting foreign direct investment and modern technologies to the industry, deep processing of local raw materials, import substitution, competitive and high value in export markets. expanding the production of modern electrical engineering and electrical household products with added value

Systematic measures are being implemented in the republic to develop and modernize the electrical engineering industry, create new types of modern electrical engineering and electrical household products production facilities, increase the investment and export potential of the industry, as well as provide comprehensive support to local manufacturers [9].

Currently, in many countries of the world, digitalization has become one of the main priorities of strategic development along with innovation policy. For example, the Republic of Uzbekistan is implementing the state program "Digital Uzbekistan", where the main goal is to improve the quality of life of the population through the use of digital technologies, to accelerate the pace of economic development, to create conditions that

allow the economy of Uzbekistan to move to a fundamentally new trajectory of development, which should ensure the creation of a digital economy of the future.

Materials And Methods

According to the forecasts of the world's leading experts, almost more than a quarter of the world economy will be digital by 2025. All spheres and sectors of the economy will be subject to digitalization: the public sector, the sector of large industrial enterprises, the sector of small and medium-sized businesses, and the social sphere. In other words, interaction schemes in digitalization will work: "B2B" (business – business); "B2C" (business – consumer); "C2C" (consumer – consumer); G2B (government - business); G2C (government - consumer). Considering this aspect, each country in the developed strategic plans should strive to provide for the development of those sectors of the economy that play the greatest role in the digitalization of production and economic processes.

The following should be defined as the main directions of development of the electrical industry:

- production of energy-saving, cheap and high-quality electrical engineering and electrical household products that replace imports, taking into account the needs of the domestic market;
- introduction of advanced technologies into deep processing of existing raw materials, expansion and diversification of production of finished products with high added value;
- development of mutual cooperative relations between the electrical engineering industry and other sectors of the economy, thereby increasing the level of localization of the production of components and equipment used in the electrical engineering industry;
- introducing modern methods of quality management and international standards into the electrical engineering industry, creating a certification system for domestically produced products in accordance with international requirements;
- production of new types of promising products in the electrical engineering industry, introduction of scientific research and experimental design developments and innovative ideas [10].

Understanding the Role of the Electrotechnical Industry in Development: Two Crucial Questions;

To fully comprehend the function of manufacturing in development, two critical questions must be addressed. First, what explains the phenomenon that the quicker electrotechnical production develops relative to GDP, the faster GDP appears to grow? Second, what factors contribute to the expansion of the manufacturing sector in the first place? Or, what factors limit the expansion of industrial output?

On the first question, it is worth noting that because differences in growth rates are largely explained by differences in labor productivity growth rather than differences in labor force growth rates, there must be some relationship between manufacturing sector growth and overall productivity growth. This is justified by two factors. The first is that whenever industrial production and output increase, labor resources are taken from sectors with open or disguised unemployment, such that labor transfers into

manufacturing do not reduce output in these sectors and productivity growth outside of manufacturing grows. The existence of rising returns inside industry, both static and dynamic, is a second explanation. Static returns are a feature of manufacturing that come from the size and scale of production units. When the factors of production are doubled, for example, output grows by a factor of more than two. Dynamic economies of scale are brought about through induced technological advancement and learning by doing, both of which are the outcome of production growth.

On the second topic, manufacturing production is not bound by supply-side resources; rather, a budding industrial sector need a market to sell to. Manufacturing expansion relies on agricultural demand in the early phases of development. Agriculture is the largest 'external' (independent) sector at this stage, emphasizing the importance of increased agricultural production in providing buying power and a growing market for industrial goods. However, the role of agriculture as an autonomous market for industrial goods declines with time, and exports eventually take over. In this regard, the ability of exporters to fund imports is a limitation.

Results and discussion

A digitalization of the economy for developing countries is a relatively new and promising direction. In the science of these countries, research has been conducted only to a small extent on the conceptual apparatus of digitalization of economic processes, the impact of digitalization processes on economic growth, the level of innovation and competitiveness of the economy, and social processes. The existing potential for predicting the prospects of digital development has also been studied to a small extent. The process of building a digital economy, relative to global digitalization processes – is a new stage in the development of developing countries based on the principles of “Industry 4.0” trends. It is important to build the main organizational and economic mechanisms for the development of digitalization at the macro and micro levels.

According to generally accepted encyclopedic data, the digital economy is the process of functioning of an economic system based on the complex application of computer technology, software, digital communications, and network communications [1].

The digital economy covers all subsystems of government activity, including:

- production of goods and services;
- distribution of goods and services;
- consumption of goods and services;
- cash flow (digital currency);
- social processes in society.

There is a different range of scientific approaches to understanding the essence of the digital economy. Thus, the digital economy is considered in the following interpretations:

- information economy;
- knowledge economy;
- innovative economy;
- e-economy;
- cybernetic economy.

Organizational and economic mechanisms for designing the development of the digital economy can be created and designed at the state (macroeconomic) level, as well as at the meso- and microeconomic levels.

Although the processes of digitalization at all economic levels can be carried out simultaneously, in modern theory, the first stage of digitalization should relate to the macroeconomic level.

The following measures to support the enterprises of the electrical engineering industry by the Export Promotion Agency should be introduced:

Until January 1, 2024, 50% of the cost of road, rail and air transport for the export of electrical engineering and electrical household products to all countries, including neighboring countries, but 15% of the export value of products (without transport costs) in road transport, railway providing subsidies for road transport in the amount of no more than 20%;

collateral for obtaining guarantees from local commercial banks regarding making (returning) advance payments within the framework of competitions (tenders), fulfilling contract terms in foreign currency, and ensuring warranty periods for delivered goods (works, services) regardless of funding sources providing guarantees up to 50% of the guarantee amount, but not exceeding 3 million US dollars.

The Government Commission on Export and Investment Development (S.U. Umurzakov) should approve the procedure for implementation of the support measures provided for in this paragraph within one month.

Profit tax and property tax for electrotechnical enterprises whose income from the sale of electrical engineering products is not less than 80 percent of their total income at the end of the reporting period from April 1, 2021 to January 1, 2024 to give tax benefits in the form of a 50% reduction in rates.

Funds allocated to the Fund from the State budget of the Republic of Uzbekistan are used for the following purposes:

covering 50% of the expenses related to the implementation of international standards in local enterprises producing electrical engineering and electrical household products, the certification of products in accordance with the requirements of foreign markets, but the equivalent of no more than 20,000 US dollars in one case;

covering the costs of the branch enterprises exporting high-added value copper products related to the production of products and their sale to foreign markets up to 6% of the export value, based on the types of products;

financing start-up projects, participating in the formation of chartered funds (capital) of production and service enterprises in the electrical engineering industry, establishing special engineering centers and experimental design bureaus;

in order to attract potential investors for the implementation of investment projects in the production of electrical engineering and electrical household products, repair and reconstruction of vacant and unused buildings and structures and improvement of external engineering and communication systems in them, as well as in areas specialized in the electrical engineering industry establishment of industrial technology parks;

providing short-term financial guarantees to local enterprises producing electrical engineering and electrical household products for participation in tenders;

reimbursement of 50% of the expenses of the enterprises of the electrotechnical industry network related to their participation in international exhibitions and fairs, but in one case the equivalent amount is not more than 10 thousand US dollars;

to conduct marketing of electrical engineering industry network enterprises to increase the popularity of products in foreign markets, to develop pre-project documents (business plan, technical and economic bases, etc.) of network projects, as well as to study the world market and carry out marketing analysis covering up to 50 percent of the costs associated with connecting to international databases (information resources);

organization of exhibitions and fairs in the republic and foreign countries, holding seminars, preparation of presentation materials and exhibition stands for the promotion of local electrical engineering and electrical household products.

Investment in capital construction of electronic industry enterprises is one of the most important investments in the construction and development of the digital economy. These investments will ensure sustainability in the medium and strategic term of the following sectors:

- state management of the economy;
 - functioning of the banking sector;
 - higher education sector;
 - healthcare industry;
 - electric power industry;
- the military-industrial complex [3].

Creation of new production capacities and diversification of production in the electrical engineering industry in 2021-2022

№	The area where the project is located	Project name	Project initiator	Annual capacity	Project cost (thousand dollars.)	from which:			Jobs (unit)	Start-up period
						funds of the initiator	bank loans	foreign direct investments		
136	Total:			-	531 921	169 542	228 220	137 659	9 657	-
43.	I. Household appliances and other consumer products			-	177 959	51 618	86 861	39 480	4 510	-

In 2021-2022, the creation of new production capacities in the electrical engineering industry and the launch of investment projects that will be implemented as part of the production diversification program

№	Name of the area	Number of projects (unit)	including that starts up:		Cost of projects (thousand dollars.)	including for those who will be employed:		Jobs (unit)	including for those who will be employed:	
			in 2021	in 2022		in 2021	in 2022		in 2021	in 2022

Total:	136	45	91	531 921	138 095	393 826	9 657	3 010	6 647
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Financing of investment projects to be implemented within the framework of the program of creation of new production capacities and diversification of production in the electrical engineering industry in 2021-2022

№	Name of the area	On projects that will be launched in 2021				On projects that will be launched in 2022			
		Cost of projects (thousand dollars.)	from which:			Cost of projects (thousand dollars.)	from which:		
			funds of the initiator	bank loans	directly foreign investments		funds of the initiator	bank loans	directly foreign investments
	Total:	138 095	53 550	70 645	13 900	393 826	115 992	157 575	123 759

Conclusion

Studying the organizational and economic mechanisms of designing the development of the digital economy, we can conclude that the processes of digitalization requires attention, both from the private sector of the economy and from the state. At the same time, the formation of the ecosystem of the digital economy is inherent in the state, which is endowed with tools for implementing policies at the macroeconomic level. Without the participation of microeconomics entities – enterprises, firms, companies, building a digital economy is also impossible since their digitalization processes are part of the ecosystem. At the same time, the digital economy should have a synergy of private and public capital.

Concentrate on infrastructure development: establish a clean land fund and the best conditions for infrastructure investors. Accelerate investment in technological infrastructure in industrial zones and clusters, as well as the formation of electronics industry clusters; Implement policies to promote and support businesses in developing industrial zones and clusters specializing in electronics and related sectors.

Improving environmental protection: The use, renovation, and protection of the environment are inextricably linked to the purpose of industrial growth. Failure to authorize or award construction licenses for investment projects, as well as carrying out construction without conducting an environmental impact assessment; Environmental protection propagation, education, and awareness raising Housing for employees, hospitals, and schools are examples of policies that prioritize, encourage, and enhance the social security system.

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Хурматли ҳамкасабалар “Al-Ferganus” нашриёти ва “Xalqaro nazariy va amaliy tadqiqotlar jurnali” электрон журнали Ўзбекистон таълим хизматлари бозорида ўзининг фаолиятини бошлаганлигини маълум қиламиз.

Ажойиб имкониятдан сиз биринчилар қаторида фойдаланиб илмий нашрларингизни чоп этишингиз мумкин.

“Al-Ferganus” нашриётимиз томонидан Сиз тақдим этган дарслик, ўқув қўлланма, монография ва илмий рисоаларга ISBN, Doi халқаро рақамли идентификаторларни бириктириш, уларнинг электрон замонавий андозадаги муқовалар ва ишланмаларнинг электрон макетини яратиш, нашриётда эълон қилинган ишларни электрон ахборот нашрларида жойлаштириш хизматлари кўрсатилади.

Бизнинг нашриётимизнинг бошқа нашриётлардан фарқи шундаки, тезкор ва сифатли хизмат кўрсатамиз ҳамда энг асосийси биз Сизнинг ишларингизни Алишер Навоий номидаги Ўзбекистон Миллий кутубхонаси ва Россия Миллий кутубхонаси фондларига бепул жойлашга шунингдек, Россия илмий иқтибослик индекси (РИНЦ ва E - library) платформасига, CrossRef базаларига шартнома асосида жойлаштиришга кўмаклашамиз.

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